

Studies on Fe(II) and Cd(II) Chelates of L-Lysine Monohydrochloride

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L-Lysine monohydrochloride has been investigated as a ligand and it has been found that it forms 1:1 chelates with Cd(II) and Fe(II). The two chelates have been isolated and their formulas determined on the basis of chemical analysis. The I.R. data and magnetic measurements have been used to assign structure to the chelates.

THE survey of literature reveals that L-lysine monohydrochloride as a ligand has not been systematically studied. Kaezmarek and Marion¹ have found that lysine forms complexes with nickel in the molar ratio of 1:1 and 2:1. The formation of double salt of optically active L-lysine monohydrochloride with lithium chloride is reported². Preliminary studies on the complexes of lysine with cobalt³, molybdenum⁴, copper⁵ and chromium⁶ have also been carried out. The present communication reports on the isolation and characterization of Fe(II) and Cd(II) chelates of L-lysine monohydrochloride.

Experimental

Cadmium sulphate, ferrous ammonium sulphate (B.D.H., AnalaR) and L-lysine monohydrochloride (Switzerland, Fluka) were used without further purification. Their solutions were prepared in water distilled over alkaline potassium permanganet.

All conductance measurements were made with a conductivity meter type LBR/B (W.T.W., German make) and pH measurements on Beckman pH-meter standardised with phthalate and borax buffer. Magnetic measurements of chelates were done at room temperature ($25 \pm 1^\circ$) on Gouy's magnetic balance.

Isolation of chelates studied :

10 ml of aqueous solution (0.1 M) of the ligand was slowly added to a beaker containing 10 ml of aqueous solutions (0.1 M) of ferrous ammonium sulphate and cadmium sulphate. The pH of the resulting mixture was raised to about 8.0 by the addition of NaOH solution drop by drop. The mixture was warmed up, allowed to stand overnight and then concentrated over a water bath. On cooling the complex precipitated. The complexes were filtered, washed with ice cold

water, recrystallized from distilled water and finally dried in vacuum desiccator over anhydrous calcium chloride.

Results and Discussion

The composition of both the chelates was established using Job's method of continuous variation⁷ and also molar ratio⁸ method. For Job's method, equimolar solutions (0.002 M) of the metal and the ligand were mixed and their ratio was varied from 1:9 to 9:1. The conductance measurements of the resulting solutions revealed that both the metals form complexes with the ligand in the molar ratio of 1:1.

The molecular formulae assigned to complexes on the basis of analytical results as given below also show that metal to ligand ratio is 1:1.

(i) Cd(II) complex (Cadmium lysinato chloride) :

	C	H	N	Cl	Cd
Found	16.44	6.51	5.59	7.90	25.22 percent
Calcd. for (Cd C ₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂)Cl.8H ₂ O	16.54	6.65	6.42	8.1	25.68 percent

(ii) Fe(II) Chelate :

	C	H	N	Cl	Fe
Found	19.52	7.00	7.62	9.52	15.00 percent
Calcd. for (FeC ₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂)Cl.7H ₂ O	19.88	7.45	7.74	9.80	15.46 percent

I.R. and magnetic data

The following principal bands were obtained in the I.R. spectra of the ligand and its chelates

	$\nu(\text{NH}_3^+\text{Cl})$	$\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO}^-)$	$\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO}^-)$
Ligand	2100 cm^{-1}	1560 cm^{-1}	1390 cm^{-1}
Cd-Chelate	—	1590 cm^{-1}	1360 cm^{-1}
Fe-Chelate	—	1610 cm^{-1}	1400 cm^{-1}

Cadmium lysinatochloride

Iron Lysinatochloride

The band at 2100 cm^{-1} in the ligand and assigned to $-\text{NH}_3^+\text{Cl}$ group⁹ disappears in chelates due to the fact that the chelates were isolated at pH of about 8.0 and, therefore the $-\text{NH}_3^+$ group got deprotonated. It is well known that amino acids¹⁰ exist as dipolar (Zwitter ions) in crystalline state and therefore two relevant I.R. bands of amino acids from coordination point of view are antisymmetric and symmetric stretching frequency of carboxyl group. Of these two the antisymmetric COO^- stretching frequency is much more sensitive¹¹ than the symmetric one and its value in a complex is a function of the mass, radius, charge and electronegativity of the metal. Thus any shift in $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO}^-)$ is taken as a sufficient measure of the carboxylate group coordinating to the metal. It is seen from the table already given that $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO}^-)$ in Cd(II) and Fe(II) chelates is significantly increased to higher value indicating coordination of the carboxyl group to the metal. The increase in frequency is due to formation of M-O bond¹⁰⁻¹² which lengthens one C-O band, making thereby both the oxygen atoms non-equivalent. Thus by M-O bond formation the $\nu_{\text{asymmetry}}$ of COO^- group is increased and thereby $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO}^-)$ is also increased. It is therefore, expected that more the covalent character of M-O band, more would shift in ν_{asym} to higher frequency. Our results do indicate that $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO}^-)$ for Fe(II) chelate is higher than that of Cd-chelate. This is due to the fact that Fe^{2+} being smaller in size forms a bond with oxygen which is of much greater covalent character.

The I.R. spectra of the ligand also has a broad band in the region 2800-3400 cm^{-1} evidently due to O-H and N-H stretches and it almost remains intact

in the spectra of chelates. On the basis of above I.R. evidence the chelates may be assigned following structures.

The molar conductance of the chelates were found to be 75 and 50 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ for Cd(II) and Fe(II)-chelates which confirms their uni-univalent type electrolytic structure. The presence of chloride ions outside the coordination sphere was further confirmed by silver nitrate test.

Both the Fe(II) and Cd(II) chelates were found to be diamagnetic and had effective magnetic moment values of 0.50 and 0.57 B.M. indicating the absence of unpaired electron. The absence of unpaired electron in case of Fe(II) chelate indicates that Fe(II) forms inner orbital low spin complex through d^2sp^3 hybridisation and its oxidation state remains +2 during chelation.

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